

Infrared Thermography Medical in Distal Tibia Dysphysis in a Patient with Pseudoarthrosis Diagnosis - Case Study

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Abstract— Infrared thermography is a diagnostic method that can be used to monitor patients with bone fractures. The aim of the present study was to investigate alterations in the thermal pattern in diaphyseal tibial fracture with the use of external fixator Ilisarov, in a patient diagnosed with pseudoarthrosis of tibia in 2019. Thermal imaging series of tibia diaphysis region were acquired at position lying in the dorsal decubitus position in the anteroposterior incidence. Thermal imaging was acquired through a FLIR®Systems Inc. Professional T 530 camera with thermal resolution of 0.08 °C and 0.1 mm spatial resolution, with the actual integrated resolution being 320 X 240 pixels, 16 bits at 60 Hz. There was a significant difference of 0.90C in the thermal values in the symptomatic distal point of the tibia corresponding to the fitting of the rings of the external fixator Ilisarov, as well as changes in the ten segmented portions of the whole tibial shaft with mean temperature between 20°C to 25°C . The ringing portion of the rings in the distal tibia demonstrated a decrease in temperature compatible with less local vascularization. The results suggest that the diagnosis by medical thermography can be used as a good method of follow-up and clinical follow-up in diaphyseal tibial fractures in pseudoarthrosis diagnoses, minimizing the patient's exposure to subsequent examinations with ionizing radiations.

Keywords- *Thermography, Diaphyseal Fractures, Pseudoarthrosis*

I. INTRODUCTION

Infrared thermography (IT) is a diagnostic technique that captures and measures the radiation that is emitted by the body, providing an image of the thermal distribution of the skin surface [1,2].

Infrared radiation is invisible to the naked eye and indicates the degree of molecular agitation [2]. The thermal image is dependent on the emission of radiation from the surface of the skin and with the help of a special camera, an accurate thermal mapping of the human body can be achieved by converting the thermal energy emitted by the

body into electrical signals that are scanned and presented in image form [3,4].

This diagnostic technique has been increasingly used to record thermal and physical body patterns, monitoring the distribution of skin temperature for evaluation of normal and pathological thermal physiological processes, characterized by increased or decreased skin temperature, as well as diagnostic method [5,6,7].

The ability of fractured bone to regenerate to bone healing itself can be compromised when there is no sufficient osteogenic reaction in the fracture callus. In long bones, the prevalence of these fractures occurs 18.5% in tibial diaphysis and 1.7% in femur [8].

Pseudoarthrosis is the term used to designate non-consolidation of a fracture, when the bone repair process for some reason ceased to act [9]. The treatment is surgical with the placement of Ilisarov technique external fixators to promote bone healing. The criteria for clinical follow-up of pseudoarthrosis of long bone fractures are based on specific parameters of physical examination in the clinical evaluation, analysis of radiographs in at least two incidences with interval of two weeks between each acquisition of radiographic images [10]. However, there is disagreement among surgeons regarding the criteria adopted, being a critical decision in the area of orthopedics / traumatology.

Thermography is a method of image evaluation that can also be used to monitor bone lesions and the regeneration process at early stages until the final consolidation stages [11,12,13,14].

The process of healing, formation and bone remodeling is directly related to metabolic and vascular changes at the fracture site. Observing the peak temperature in the period corresponding to the inflammatory phase of the bone regeneration process will support the physician in treatment decisions [15]. The authors [16,17] proposed the use of thermography for follow-up and evolution of the healing process of this traumatic lesion.

Thermography presents itself as a complementary analysis tool for different stages of healing and interpretation of these medical imaging results, as it is presented as a safe, non-harmful, non-invasive and painless technique, since no ionizing radiation is used to obtain the image [18,19,20].

The study [21] demonstrated that the application of thermal imaging may be useful in detecting distal radius and ulna fractures in children's pulses, presenting a sensitivity of only 96.8% when compared to X-rays. Compared to clinical examination, the results demonstrate sensitivity of up to 96.7%. Thus, thermographic parameters may indicate alterations in bone healing delay, presenting as a diagnostic method to minimize the subjectivity of medical reports and provide additional information in diagnoses performed by conventional imaging methods.

The aim of the present study was to investigate alterations in the thermal pattern in tibia fracture with diagnosis of pseudoarthrosis with the use of external fixator Ilisarov.

II. METHODOLOGY

A. Sample

This research complied with the ethical recommendations of Resolution 466/12 and was approved by the Research Ethics Committee of the Federal Technological University of Paraná - UTFPR, CAEE: 36614014.0.0000.5547, under the number of opinion 3,014,748 in November 2018 and by the Committee of Ethics in Research of Hospital das Clínicas of the Federal University of Paraná - UFPR, CAEE: 94622718.0.3001.0096, under the number of opinion 3,067,005 in December 2018. The sample consisted of a volunteer from the city of Curitiba, Brazil, aged 34 years, height 1.68 m and body mass of 68.0 kg. Young male with diagnosis of pseudoarthrosis of the tibia occurred in March 2019.

B. Conduct at the Medical Thermography Laboratory

In May 2019, in the Departamento de Trauma e Reconstrução do Hospital das Clínicas da Universidade Federal do Parná UTFPR, the volunteer underwent thermal adaptation in the same room where the thermal images of the region of the tibia and fibula were collected, thus being climatized at least a minimum of 15 minutes before the thermographic collections, in a sitting position with the hands relaxed and supported on the thigh.

In order to adapt to the climate the volunteer was dressed in T-shirt and comfortable shorts, with controlled ambient temperature at 21°C.

The temperature of the Consultório Médico was maintained at approximately 21°C with closed doors and windows, following the recommendation of the International Academy of Clinical Thermology (IACT) and the Brazilian Association of Thermology (ABRATERM) for infrared image detection.

The air velocity was lower than 0.2 m / s, controlled by a digital anemometer, avoiding evaporation and consequent cutaneous thermal loss due to forced convection, by means of care of closed doors and windows and reduced movement around the researched volunteer. Black curtains between the evaluated subject and the windows, so that the external light did not influence the capture of the images.

Fluorescent lights were standardized in the environment of the thermogram collections. The volunteer was evaluated

in the afternoon, so that there were no thermal changes due to variations in the circadian cycle [22].

C. Acquiring Thermal Imaging

Regarding the capture of the thermal images of the fracture region of the tibia. The volunteer was dressed in a t-shirt and comfortable shorts that did not compress the skin, in the sequence was positioned comfortably lying on his back (supine position) on a clinical table (stretcher), with arms extended along the body.

Cushions with cotton cloth pillowcases were used to protect the head in order to provide greater comfort during the collection of thermal images. The legs were extended and hypoallergenic disposable markers were used for individual use and fixed to the anterior and lateral tibia to delimit the study area and respective points of interest (ROI) for recording the skin surface temperatures (TP).

D. Equipment and Instruments

The thermal imaging was taken by means of an FLIR®Systems Inc. Professional T-530 câmera with 0.08 ° thermal and 0.1 mm spatial resolution, with the actual integrated resolution being 320 X 240 pixels, 16-bit at 60 Hz. The following parameters were adjusted: skin emissivity of 98% for human body [2], reflected temperature, air relative humidity below 60%.

All images were taken with the camera fixed e suporte técnico for thermographic camera, for collections in the incidences antero-posterior to the height of 80 cm corresponding aligned with the median line of the tibial fracture region and (region of interest) with a 90° angle, and perpendicular to the camera lens [23].

E. Thermographic Image Processing

The thermal mapping and image interpretation were performed using the software MatLab® 2018a (MathWorks, Inc), by extracting histograms from images thermal.

The data were exported in Microsoft Office Excel® tables for the construction of Boxplot-type dispersion of temperature averages and three-dimensional (3D) scatter plots of the ten portions (slices) of the region of interest of the tibial distal diaphysis.

III. RESULTS

There was a significant difference of 0.9°C in the thermal values of tibia distal between the rings of the external fixator Ilisarov, according to Figure 1.

Figure 1: Right tibia infra-structure image with Ilisarov fastener
Source: Own Authorship.

IV. DISCUSSION

For the extraction of the thermogram data, the regions of interest for the analysis of the thermal differences between the insertion rings of the Ilizarov external fixator in distal tibial diaphysis were segmented and delimited according to Figure 2.

Figure 2: Segmentation of the image and delimitation of the region of interest of distal tibial diaphysis.

The average temperatures presented thermographic image varied from 20°C to 25°C, lower temperatures were found at the insertion limits of the Ilizarov fastener rings, with a mean temperature of 20 °C.

The lower region of the distal tibia presents a mean temperature of 24°C, considered high for this bone portion, and may characterize an inflammation of bone tissue, according to data presented in Figures 3 and 4.

Figure 3: Mean temperature of the region of interest in distal tibia diaphysis between the rings of the Ilizarov fixator.

Figure 4: Graph of dispersion of temperature mean in distal tibia diaphysis between the rings of the Ilizarov fixator.

Bone consolidation is a simple biological phenomenon that occurs in phases: formation of hematoma, inflammation, angiogenesis, formation of cartilage and, finally, bone remodeling [24,25].

We highlight the inconvenience in the follow-up of pseudoarthrosis in tibia diaphysis adverse effects of the ionizing radiation that the patient is exposed with the accomplishment of numerous radiological examinations for follow-up and clinical monitoring evolution of the bone lesion.

The frequency of occurrence of fractures as well as the complexity of bone and muscle damage are very important aspects for traumatologists. Incorrect medical judgment and treatment and accompaniment failures may lead to poor results regarding bone healing response [26].

The results showed that the thermography examination showed evidencing the metabolic alterations still present in the sites of formation of the bone callus offering additional data in the support direction treatment decisions and clinical evolution of traumatic lesions minimizing continued exposure to ionizing radiation. Values above 0.5°C are considered pathological thermal changes according to the International Academy of Clinical Thermology.

A local increase in temperature during compression and distraction of the fracture focus and correction of the angular deformity of the limb with the Ilizarov technique are associated with increased metabolic process at all stages of bone regeneration and remodeling.

According to the study conducted in Croatia [27], which evaluated temperature differences in pediatric trauma in patients aged 4 to 14 years, the authors' research demonstrated the use of thermography in the evolutionary follow-up of bone fracture consolidation after 7, 14 and 21 days after the appearance of the bone lesion.

In continuity to the studies on the applicability of thermography in bone consolidation, the study carried out in Russia [28] stands out with 18 patients who underwent repair surgery. The sample consisted of (9 women and 9 men) between 12 and 74 years, the bone lengthening performed by the Ilizarow method. The extended segments were: the lower part of the leg - in 13 patients, the thigh of 4 patients and the forearm - in 1 patient. The assessment of healing status was done as part of periodic x-ray outpatient checks comparing them with thermograms. The results of this study corroborate with the findings of the hourly case study which also evidences temperature changes in the insertions of the Ilizarov fastener rings.

Based on the radiographic exams, thermal indices were determined - temperature difference of the extended end in place of its extension and symmetrical end in the same level and the temperature difference of the extended end in the location of its extension and in selected near points. This study demonstrated that the thermographic examination is a valuable complement to traditional imaging methods and can be successfully used in orthopedics and traumatology.

Thus, another study, which also corroborates the applicability of thermography in bone lesions, [16] carried out an investigation of the thermal changes during bone healing with 25 patients aged between 50 and 80 years who

presented with distal fractures in the radial bone with thermal imaging on the day of fracture, after three days, after five days, after 11 days and after 23 weeks of follow-up.

The results of the research demonstrated significant temperature changes during the healing process of the radial bone fractures and supported the initial hypothesis of the investigators that the thermography examination is feasible in the clinical practice of orthopedics as an excellent method for monitoring the evolution of the bone healing process.

According to a pilot study [29] that analyzed 476 thermal images of bone stress in Australian Army soldiers during three months of research into the detection of pathology of stress fractures in the legs of Australian Army basic trainees, results focal changes in the tibial and fibular bones and allowed control in the development of biomechanical stress fractures in lower limbs during military training.

In this way, thermography presents itself as a complementary diagnostic tool in the evolutionary follow-up of the different stages of cicatrization, presenting as a safe, non-harmful, non-invasive and painless technique, since no ionizing radiation is used to obtain the image [18,19,20].

The findings of the present study demonstrated temperature differences in the evaluations of the insertion of the Ilisarov fixator rings in the tibial shaft in the proximal and distal portions, corroborate with the previous studies presented and denote the possibility of medical thermography as an alternative for immediate diagnosis and in the evolutionary follow – of diaphyseal tibial fractures with the diagnosis of pseudarthrosis, allowing the reduction of differences in medical decisions and treatment options.

V. CONCLUSION

The results indicate that medical thermography can be used as a good follow-up method in traumatology and orthopedics, but further investigations are necessary with larger samples of patients diagnosed with diaphyseal fractures of tibia with diagnosis of pseudoarthrosis in different stages of bone consolidation, allowing precise information of the thermal profile during the cicatrization process.

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